

Week	Dates	NY	CA	FL	TX	MA	MS							
1	Jan 19-25	0	1	0	0	0	0							
2	Jan 26-Feb 1	0	2	0	0	1	0							
3	Feb 2-Feb 8	0	2	0	0	0	0							
4	Feb 9-Feb 15	0	4	0	0	0	0							
5	Feb 16-Feb 22	0	4	0	0	0	0							
6	Feb 23-Feb 29	0	18	0	0	0	0							
7	Mar 1-Mar 7	52	72	14	1	66	0							
8	Mar 8-Mar14	467	151	101	0	218	5							
9	Mar 15-Mar 21	9853	1039	662	471	1711	134							
10	Mar 22-Mar 28	41990	3698	3000	1873	4893	523							
11	Mar 29-Apr 4	69305	7734	7774	4141	8292	792							
12	Apr 5-Apr 11	70557	8878	6957	6549	12147	1187							
13	Apr 12-Apr 18	52107	9083	6998	5579	15319	1332							
14	Apr 19-Apr 25	43529	11966	5347	4998	14880	1744							
15	Apr 26-May 2	29276	11062	4624	6839	12447	1723							
16	May 3-May 9	19628	13452	4538	7857	9898	1937							
17	May 10-May 16	14177	10566	4810	8667	7551	1745							
18	May 17-May 23	11910	13933	5316	6802	6059	1882							
19	May 24-May 30	9584	17533	5297	8113	3598	2224							
20	May 31-Jun 6	7593	18811	7334	11607	2481	1810							
21	Jun 7-Jun 13	5038	22153	10794	12540	1743	2309							
22	Jun 14-Jun 20	4498	26975	20245	23058	1330	1293							
23	Jun 21-Jun 27	4659	38844	38748	36004	1288	4890							
24	Jun 28-Jul 4	4793	44189	57507	48347	1145	4468							
25	Jul 5-Jul 11	4823	64390	64459	60719	1496	4745							
26	Jul 12-Jul 18	5503	62157	83058	72291	1588	6427							
27	Jul 19-Jul 25	4937	64381	76942	63192	1736	9135							
28	Jul 26-Aug 1	3982	60247	65517	55986	2094	8900							
29	Aug 2-Aug 8	4278	47858	46549	55774	2062	6765							
30	Aug 9-Aug 15	3705	61495	43060	50257	2008	5109							
31	Aug 16-Aug 22	4241	45156	27960	41304	2069	5513							
32	Aug 23-Aug 29	4213	36580	21406	35974	2284	4761							
33	Aug 30-Sep 5	4356	35183	24864	29319	1661	4449							
34	Sep 6-Sep 12	5016	23429	17704	22397	2344	3142							
35	Sep 13-Sep 19	5627	24769	19662	30243	2641	3467							
36	Sep 20-Sep 26	5918	24643	17449	48230	2869	3590							
37	Sep 27-Oct 3	8734	18835	15909	32783	4253	2938							
38	Oct 4-Oct 10	10090	23174	14330	31055	4037	4471							

Source:
 Johns Hopkins University, COVID-19 Dashboard by the Center for
 Systems Science and Engineering. Available from:
<https://www.arcgis.com/apps/opsdashboard/index.html#/bda7594740fd40299423467b48e9ecf6>
 (Accessed on: October 30, 2020).

Week	Dates	NY	CA	FL	TX	MA	MS
39	Oct 11-Oct 17	9810	21632	23560	32565	4590	5370
40	Oct 18-Oct 24	11525	30227	23770	40946	6558	5082
41	Oct 25-Oct 31	14029	28656	26296	45220	9088	5072
42	Nov 1-Nov 7	18457	38138	34530	88603	11000	5725

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